

CONNECTIVITY OF PEOPLE'S MARKET PROTECTION POLICIES IN THE ERA OF SOCIETY 5.0 IN INCREASING REGIONAL ECONOMIC GROWTH IN DISADVANTAGED DISTRICTS OF BANTEN PROVINCE

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Abstract

The transformation of life is going quickly so that changes are felt by the community as a result of the progress of the times that have a positive and negative impact. It is undeniable that in the 5.0 era, traditional markets experience many challenges, namely competing with virtual markets and modern markets that are starting to stand in every place, especially in regions, cities, and districts in the Banten Province area. The government must act quickly in maintaining traditional markets to maintain market balance to reduce poverty levels. Traditional markets are gradually shrinking, affecting economic activities. This study uses a qualitative approach with the collection of primary and secondary data. The results of the study show that policy connectivity is needed to synergize traditional market management in order to adapt to the needs and demands of the community so that it can bring the welfare of the local community to improve the regional economy so that it can catch up. Some of the things that need to be done through; (1) Digitalization of the People's Market, (2) Education and Training, (3) Strategic Partnerships, (4) Regulatory and Policy Support, (5) Market Promotion and Education, (6) Quality Improvement and Product Diversification, (7) Monitoring and Evaluation.

Keywords: Policy Connectivity, Traditional Markets, Economic Growth, Society 5.0 Era.

INTRODUCTION

The development of digital technology that is happening today triggers people around the world regardless of age to be interconnected with each other (Ornelas Sánchez & Vera-Martínez, 2023). This development gave rise to a new generation called screenager (Prasetia & Lestari, 2023). Screenager is a group of people who have a variety of digital devices and are never satisfied with certain digital services (Caporaso, 2024). The middle class in Indonesia has reached 74 million people and this number will increase in 2020. In addition, 93% of digital consumers have a mobile phone, of which 77% already use a smartphone (Hauke-Lopes et al., 2023). Related to this, the correlation is that with the increasing number of users of digital technology and services, it is also accompanied by consumer behavior that wants a better digital experience (Ahmad & Fikriya, 2023; Florensia K. Lamanele¹, Daisy S. M. Engka², 2024; Qurrata et al., 2022). One of the impacts of technology is the emergence of online shopping providing different product information that can influence consumer purchase decisions (Firdaus et al., 2022). For example, product attributes, sales ratings, promotional information

and customer reviews are usually displayed on websites, the most popular e-commerce websites such as Amazon.com, Taobao.com, etc (Yu et al., 2020).

The development of traditional markets in Indonesia shows unpleasant data that there has been a shift in public interest Indonesia from traditional markets to modern markets (Habibah et al., 2023; Irbah & Khairina, 2023a; Prasetya & Lestari, 2023; Rahmadi & Hastuti, 2023). This is marked by the emergence of modern markets that are growing rapidly by around 31.4 percent, and on the contrary, traditional markets have decreased by around 8.1 percent. This condition has a negative impact on the number of sales in traditional markets which decreased by around 16.3-24 percent, and also the amount of revenue from traditional markets which decreased by around 17.5-30 percent as a consequence of a decrease in the number of customers by around 29-32 percent (Haryanto et al., 2019). This can be seen in the following data:

Picture: Indonesia Enters the Top 10 Countries with the Most Online Shopping

No.	Nama Data	Nilai
1	Thailand	66,9
2	Korea Selatan	65,8
3	Turki	64,7
4	Uni Emirat Arab	64,3
5	Meksiko	62,1
6	Malaysia	61,9
7	China	61,1
8	Inggris	60,9
9	India	59,3
10	Indonesia	59,3

Sumber: *Databoks.katadata.id*, 2024

According to the latest We Are Social report, in January 2024 there are around 56.1% of global internet users who usually shop online every week (Bui & Nguyen, 2019). If broken down by country, the proportion of internet users who often shop *online* is the most in Thailand, which is 66.9% (Wimalasinghe & Gooneratne, 2019). In second place is South Korea, with 65.8% of its internet users shopping *online* at least once a week (Ghorbel et al., 2022). Next are Turkey, the United Arab Emirates, Mexico, Malaysia, China, and the United Kingdom, with proportions as seen in the graph (Hauke-Lopes et al., 2023). Indonesia ranks 9th on this list, with the proportion of internet users who shop *online* every week at 59.3%, equivalent to India (Annur, 2024).

In this thinking, traditional markets are regional economic assets as well as the glue of social relations in society (Nengsih & Kurniawan, 2021). The presence of modern markets is evidence of modernization (Ariani et al., 2019). This can be seen through the development of modern

markets such as supermarkets, minimarkets, supermarkets, hypermarkets, malls and others (Manzanaris et al., 2018). Not to go unnoticed is the development of minimarket franchises has also increased, such as Alfamart, Alfamidi, Indomaret and others which provide a variety of needs ranging from food, beverages, beauty, including basic necessities and others (Dakhoir, 2018; Firdaus et al., 2022; Jumanah et al., 2019; Setyasih, 2022). The modern market is a reality that cannot be denied because it is an implication of the presence of modernization in society. Modern markets are able to attract public attention, starting from market locations, public space security, services, cleanliness, and comfort for consumers (Fatimah, 2023).

The ever-growing online shopping market allows customers to use information technology with the aim of conducting shopping activities According to data collected by eMarketer (2014), retail e-commerce sales increased to \$2.304 trillion in 2017 which is equivalent to an increase of 24.8 percent compared to 2016. eMarketer (2015,2014) reported that digital retail sales in the Asia Pacific region grew 10 percent faster compared to the same rate as in 2016. and shows that more than half of online retail sales occur in the Asia-Pacific region. This indicates the existence of dynamic e-commerce in the Asia-Pacific region driven by China, India, and Indonesia For Indonesia, the e-commerce market is expected to soon become the third largest in Southeast Asia (Dewi et al., 2020) E-commerce has become a great opportunity that continues to grow in the middle class. Recently, China has overtaken the United States as the most powerful country in the largest e-commerce market, representing more than half of global online sales (Thiebaut, 2019)

E-commerce Users in Indonesia in 2023

Sumber: <https://goodstats.id>, 2024

Based on Goodstats data, Indonesia has 178.94 million online market or e-commerce consumers in 2022. When compared to 158.65 million users in the previous year, there was an increase of 12.79%. Based on current trends, it seems that the number of e-commerce consumers in Indonesia is increasing. By the end of 2023, it is estimated that there will be 196.47 million users. And it is estimated that in the next four years, the number of ecommerce consumers will continue to increase (nur aeni, MH Ainulyaqin, 2024).

E-Commerce is a form of technological advancement that we can feel now. We must be familiar with the existence of E-Commerce, especially people who like to shop online on the internet. The development of information technology today is increasingly intensively supported by supporting infrastructure that has been built by the government and the private sector. Along with the penetration of technology into all areas of life, the penetration of information technology today has resulted in the development of electronic commerce or e-commerce (Nida et al., 2024).

Meanwhile, sales in traditional markets with the existence of e-commerce have led to a decrease in the number of consumer visitors in traditional markets, resulting in a decrease in sales levels. This is due to the sales competition that occurs on e-commerce platforms that offer very large discount promotions to consumers, thus having a huge impact on merchants in traditional markets. The decline in the value of products or goods on e-commerce platforms makes traditional markets less attractive for consumers to visit. In addition, not only traders in traditional markets feel the negative impact of e-commerce, such as parking attendants also feel the impact of e-commerce which results in a decrease in the revenue of the services they offer due to the lack of visitors, even the Tanah Abang market, which is one of the largest textile markets in Southeast Asia, also experiences a lack of visitors. And the following is the prediction data for the number of E-commerce users in Indonesia (nur aeni, MH Ainulyaqin, 2024).

Image: E-Commerce User Predictions in Indonesia 2024

Sumber: Data.tempo.co.id

The growth of e-commerce in Indonesia can also be explained by the ease of payment offered by internet retailers. The good prospects of e-commerce in Indonesia are definitely good news for the business and the country. E-commerce is projected to play a more important role in strengthening Indonesia's economy. Many local stakeholders in the e-commerce industry can take advantage of its development. Manufacturers, raw material suppliers, logistics companies, infrastructure providers, distributors, sellers, and buyers are all major beneficiaries of the growth of the e-commerce industry. This not only benefits local players, but also encourages the entry of many foreign investors (Febransyah & Camelia Goni, 2020)

RESEARCH METHODS

This research uses a qualitative approach. The stages of the analysis are as follows: The first stage, the collection of both primary and secondary data. In-Depth Interviews: Conduct in-depth interviews with various stakeholders, including: (1) Market Traders, to understand how policies affect their operations and what challenges they face. (2) Regional Government, to get a perspective on the implementation of policies and strategies implemented. (3) Consumers, to find out how policies impact their experience of shopping in the people's market. Second, qualitative descriptive analysis using the *Miles* and Huberman interactive model (Creswell, 2014; Matthew B Miles, Michael Huberman, 2014; Patton, 2002; Sarantoks, 1993; Steven J. Taylor, Robert Bogdan, 2016), namely data collection, data reduction, data presentation and conclusion drawn.

DISCUSSION

A. Scope of Traditional Markets

The Indonesian people have known markets, especially traditional markets, for a long time. In Indonesia, the existence of traditional markets is not just an economic matter, but further to the norms, cultural realms, as well as civilizations that have been going on for a long time in various regions in Indonesia (Haris et al., 2019). The community's economic process is mostly supported by a buying and selling process and this occurs in a traditional market (Sugeng Widodo, 2020).

The Market Function has three functions (Fuad, 2000), which are as follows: (1) The formation of market price value functions for the formation of price (value), because the market is a meeting place for sellers and buyers who then bargain with each other and finally make an agreement on a price. This price or value is a result of the buying and selling process carried out in the market. (2) Market Distribution makes it easier for producers to distribute goods with consumers directly. The distribution of goods from producers to consumers will run smoothly if the market functions properly. (3) Market Promotion is the most suitable place for producers to introduce (promote) their products to consumers. Because the market will always be visited by many people, even if they are not invited (Diva Dwiyan Putra, Elfina Doramayanti, Alimi Fajar Ramadhan, Moh Aldi Raihan, 2024; Rohmania, 2023).

According to Damsar (2005) Traditional Market Traditional markets are places where sellers and buyers meet and are marked by direct transactions between sellers and buyers, the goods consist of kiosks or stalls, lots, and the basis is open that is opened by sellers or a market manager. In this traditional market, most of them sell daily necessities such as foodstuffs in the form of fish, fruits, vegetables, eggs, meat, fish, electronics and services. In addition, it also sells traditional cakes and other Indonesian foods found in this market in the transaction process, namely traders serving buyers who come to their booths and bargaining to determine an agreement on a price with a pre-agreed amount. Markets like this can be found in residential areas that are easy to reach. Traditional markets are markets managed by the government, including cooperation with the private sector with business places in the form of shops, stands, stalls or tents owned by traders and with a buying and selling process through a bargaining process (Amar, 2024). The characteristics of the traditional market:

- 1) There is a bargaining system between sellers and buyers. Bargaining is able to have an important psychological impact on society. Everyone who plays a role in buying and selling transactions will involve all their emotions and feelings, so that social interactions and complex problems arise. Sellers and buyers compete with each other to measure the depth of each other's hearts, then a winner emerges in pricing.
- 2) There is more than one trader in the traditional market, and the trader has the right to the booth that he already owns, and has full rights to the merchandise in their respective booths, so there is no one management like in the modern market.
- 3) Most of the goods and services offered are made locally: The merchandise sold in this traditional market is produce produced by the area. Although there are some commodities taken from produce from other areas that are not far from the area, it is not imported to the outside of the island or the country.
- 4) Open and unair-conditioned areas; Unlike modern markets that have air conditioning (AC), traditional markets do not have air conditioning because they are carried out in open spaces so they do not need refrigeration.
- 5) Traditional markets are owned, built and/or managed by local governments.
- 6) Business places are diverse and united in the same location. Even though they are all in the same location, each seller's merchandise sells different items. In addition, there is also a grouping of goods according to the type of trade such as groups of fish, vegetables, fruits, spices, and meat traders (Yulianti et al., 2021).

B. The Role of People's Markets in Regional Economic Growth

The existence of this traditional market is very helpful, not only for local or central governments but also for people who depend on trading activities, because in traditional markets there are many actors who have an important meaning and strive to prosper their lives, be it traders, buyers, pelvic workers and so on (Hakim, 2019).

The main goal of traditional market development is to improve community welfare, one of the efforts to achieve this is by developing traditional markets that are starting to be unsuitable for use because development is the beginning of empowering government and community facilities (Amar, 2024)

The role of the market for the government, the market plays a very important role. The market is the driving force of a country's economy. The market exists to protect consumers and producers, especially in the determination of the Highest Retail Price (HET) policy (Endaryono & Djuhartono, 2018). The existence of a market also helps the government in setting a base price to protect producers. In addition, the market is also a means for the government to regulate the circulation of goods and improve the welfare of the community (vanya karunia mulia putri, 2021)

In addition to being a seller of various merchandise, several jobs that are open to the existence of the people's market include as suppliers of various needs of the population, transportation services for merchandise and shopping goods (as laborers), financial services (banks, cooperatives), and various other jobs, both physical and non-physical (Habibah et al., 2023). In crisis conditions, traditional markets have proven to survive and be able to serve the needs and provide services to the wider community (Rahmadi & Hastuti, 2023). Traditional markets have contributed jobs and provided livelihoods for many people. Of the total number of people's markets in Indonesia, as many as 12.6 million traders are accommodated, not including goods suppliers and market managers. Therefore, the existence of traditional markets, which are now increasingly squeezed by the rapid growth of modern markets, is important to be saved immediately. One of them is through the traditional market revitalization program (Arifin M, 2021)

Given the strategic role of the people's market, coupled with the existing problems and challenges, especially to help people who depend on the people's market for their business, the role of the government is highly expected (Irbah & Khairina, 2023). This means that it is necessary to arrange people's markets so that their existence can meet the expectations of the community by using a structuring model that combines consumer expectations and the ability of producers, in this case traders in the people's market (Arifin M, 2021).

C. The Existence of People's Markets in the 5.0 Era

Traditional markets have begun to enter the *marketplace* to market their products to be sold online so that their merchandise sells, there are even some retail traders who have started to promote and sell themselves online by using social media through whatsapp groups and others through cash on delivery promotions to attract customers to buy their products in traditional markets (Sugeng Widodo, 2020).

The use of digital technology is a must in the era of the industrial revolution 4.0 now, inevitably all people, even traditional traders, must adjust to the needs and desires of today's consumers. Therefore, all business people, like traditional traders, must start changing the way they sell, not only relying on consumers or buyers who come to the market because the number is limited and small because the scope is local, but even more broadly with an online marketing system

(Irbah & Khairina, 2023b). In this era of Civilization 5.0, humans must be able to live peacefully with technology, which means learning to use it effectively every day. The use of digital wallets for non-cash transactions is proof of technology in the economic field (Istiarohmi & Airlangga, 2024). Understanding and knowing the use of technology in the business world in the Society 5.0 Era, can improve the quality of the economy and trade, because buying and selling transactions can occur anywhere, anytime, and by anyone. As long as it is within the reach of the internet network, it will increase the interest of business actors to learn more about technology in the business world. (Hamzah et al., 2023) The current Traditional Market will enter the era of the industrial revolution 5.0, so the challenges faced lie not only in the business side but also in technological developments (Khakim, 2024).

The existence of traditional markets in this era is still very necessary. Demand for traditional markets is still very high. The community is still waiting for the continuation of traditional-based businesses. Good management will make the business bigger and survive in the era of change, the traditional market is a tax object for the government, because there are transactions that occur in the trade cycle. Tax management will have a good impact on future business development (Khakim, 2024). The presence of online markets such as marketplaces does make shopping easier which gives you your own experience. The marketplace is now also packaged in a neat, bright, airy, cool layout, all in one hand with a flat object with a modern design and makes you don't need to go anywhere (Ika Trisnawati Alawiyah, 2024). This can be seen in the following image:

Image: Traditional Market Conditions after the Onslaught of Ecommerce Rise

Source: Kompas.id, 2024

The development of modern retail from year to year which is growing rapidly and unstopably is growing rapidly in accordance with the progress of the Indonesia economy. In recent years, from 2018 to 2020, the number of retail outlets in Indonesia has experienced a normal development of around 19% for the latest retail volume development and about 6% annually for conventional quantity development (Pratama & Sanjaya, 2021).

In the face of competition from modern markets today, every traditional market is required to be able to compete with modern markets that develop like mushrooms in the rainy season, the

influence of the arrival of modern markets on traditional markets is very strong (Sugeng Widodo, 2020) The pressure of globalization brings a gap for many traditional businesses that are unable to compete internationally. Globalization also presents competition for traditional products in meeting and maintaining their niche market (Patria et al., 2020).

Then with globalization and the development of technology today, competition between traditional markets and modern retail is inevitable, of course it is important for people who have businesses or who trade are ready to compete with the outside world. Especially with the development of modern markets and online sales systems, it is not impossible that traditional market traders will dim. Therefore, new innovations or creative ideas are needed that must be raised to overcome the current free market competition (Laraswati & Niswah, 2021) some cases that traditional sellers usually face are a lack of understanding of what consumers think, and not trying to serve consumers well Most traditional sellers only focus on what can be sold, and not selling what consumers want. Satisfaction is something that is ignored by them, so individuals buy products only to meet consumer needs and not to satisfy consumer desires (Haryanto et al., 2019).

D. Existing Traditional Markets in Banten Province

Traditional markets in Banten province are quite widely spread across large areas in Banten province, including: Tangerang City, South Tangerang City, Tangerang Regency, Cilegon City, Serang City, Serang Regency, Lebak Regency, and Pandeglang Regency. The following is a list of traditional markets in the Pandeglang Regency and Lebak Regency areas which are disadvantaged areas/regions in Banten Province:

Data on Traditional Markets in Pandeglang Regency and Lebak Regency

Pandeglang Regency	Lebak Regency
Pasar Majasari	Pasar citeras
Pasar Cibaliung	Pasar malingping
Pasar Panimbang	Pasar binuangeun
Pasar Bojen	Pasar cisiih
Pasar Munjul	Pasar sukahujan
Pasar Bojong	Pasar bayah
Pasar Saketi	Pasar cikotok cibeber
Pasar Pagelaran	Pasar sukamaju cijaku
Pasar Sukaresmi	Pasar pasir kupa
Pasar Carita	Pasar kerta
Pasar Jiput	Pasar sajir cileles
Pasar Menes	Pasar gunungkendeng
Pasar Pari Mandalawangi	Pasar cilayang cirenten
Pasar Menes	Pasar ciminyak muncang
Pasar Kadu Kacang	Pasar bujal
Pasar Cipeucang	Pasar sajira
Pasar Cikeper	Pasar cikulur
Pasar Cigoong	Pasar sampay
Pasar Cadasari	Pasar maja
Pasar Kadubera	Pasar kemis ciburuy

Pasar Sodong	Pasar simpang malingping
Pasar Babad	Pasar cikatomas cilograng
Pasar Batubantar Cimanuk	Pasar warungbanten cibeber
Pasar Batu	Pasar gunung kendeng
Pasar Kadugedong	Pasar warungyuyum
Pasar Bengkung	Pasar sindang
	Pasar kopi cileles
	Pasar gunung kencana
	Pasar gajrug
	Pasar buah mandala
	Pasar rangkassbitung
	Pasar senin cilayang
	Pasar kicalung cihara
	Pasar mekarsari/ciburial
	Pasar cigemblong
	Pasar jalupang
	Pasar gajrug
	Pasar cicarucub
	Pasar bojong juru
	Pasar wanasalam
	Pasar gunungbatu cilograng
	Pasar pasirukukray cibeber
	Pasar cibuntu
	Pasar sajr
	Pasar sindang reset desa malangsari

Source: golali.id, 2024

Picture: Serang City Government Invites People to Shop at the Market

Source: serangkota.go.id, 2024

Mayor of Serang Syafrudin with the Head of the Small and Medium Business Cooperative, Industry and Trade Office (Dinkopukmperindag) of Serang City, Wahyu Nurjamil, visited the old market. Serang City Government Invites People to Shop for Basic Needs at the Old Market. This is done as one of the efforts to increase Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs)

and encourage people to shop at traditional markets. At the same time, Wahyu Nurjamil also said that the visit to the old market was a weekly routine activity carried out by the Serang City Dinkopukmperindag as one of the efforts to invite the public to shop at the traditional market. Apart from the appeal contained in the circular letter of the mayor of Serang with number: 500/1115-SETDA/VIII/2023, related to the appeal to shop at traditional markets, both all state civil servants in sub-districts, urban villages in Serang City, as well as to the wider community. Various efforts have been made, such as conducting intensive and comprehensive socialization within the Official Apparatus Organization (OPD) and mass media. He also promised that his party would carry out market renovations that would be planned in the near future to attract the interest of consumers and the public (Putra, 2023).

Image: Tangerang Traditional Market

Source: *merdeka.com*, 2024

Wawali of Tangerang City Emphasizes that Traditional Markets are Important for Residents. The reason is The development of time has made modern markets emerge. Responding to this, the Deputy Mayor of Tangerang, Sachrudin, revealed that the existence of modern markets should not erode the existence of traditional markets.

Picture: Revitalization of Pandeglang Market

Source: *Tribun Banten.com*, 2024

Two large markets in Pandeglang, namely the Rhinoceros Market and Panimbang Market, will be revitalized. The revitalization efforts at the Rhinoceros Market and Panimbang Market are carried out so that they become healthier and more modern. The Pandeglang Cooperatives, MSMEs, Industry and Trade Office (Discoperindag) allocated Rp 40 billion for each of the target markets of the revitalization because the condition of the two markets was no longer feasible and the buildings were old. It is known that the Pandeglang Rhinoceros Market and Panimbang Market have been established for 20 years. The development budget for the two markets is also not only sourced from the Regional Revenue and Expenditure Budget (APBD) but also sourced from the corporate social responsibility (CSR) of one of the companies (Nurandi, 2023).

In conclusion, the existence of Traditional Markets in Banten Province is still in demand by the community in the era of modern markets that are increasing, while the efforts made by the local government to maintain the existence of Traditional Markets are by revitalization.

Law Number 7 of 2014 on trade. The name of the traditional market has been changed to the People's Market/Main Market. The main market is an economic institution that has a strategic function, among the nodes of local economic power, contributing to the regional economy, and increasing employment opportunities. The main market, in addition to a place of transactions between sellers and buyers, is also a place of friendship between the community (Octriani et al., 2022)

As with other policies, the regulation of the governance of a traditional market in general has been regulated in Presidential Regulation Number 112 of 2007 concerning the Arrangement and Development of Traditional Markets, Shopping Centers and Modern Stores which was then followed by Ministerial Regulation Number 53 of 2008 concerning Guidelines for the Arrangement and Development of Traditional Markets, Shopping Centers and Modern Shops. Where in the Regulation it has been written how to manage and carry out the procurement of a good and professional traditional market. One of the articles in the Presidential Regulation is Article 6 which states that shopping centers are obliged to provide business places for small businesses with selling prices or rental costs that are in accordance with the capabilities of small businesses, or that can be used by small businesses through other collaborations in the context of partnerships (Juliati, 2021).

Referring to the Government Regulations of Pandeglang and Lebak Regencies, regional regulations have been stipulated, Regional Regulation of Pandeglang Regency Number 2020 concerning the implementation of markets and Regional Regulation of Lebak Regency Number 10 of 2018 concerning the Arrangement and Empowerment of Street Vendors.

D. Connectivity of People's Market Protection Policy

People's market protection policy

Traditional markets that are classified as weak economic actors both in terms of capital and management management will be marginalized and displaced. The marginalization or eviction of traditional markets will have an impact on hindering the growth of people's economic rights

both in the region and nationally. Facing the above problems, the functions and roles of the state in this case the government is very necessary. The duties and functions of the state in this case are the commitment and legal policies of the government (Seran, 2014). Behind the strategic role of traditional markets, there are problems that require the attention of policymakers and managers related to the development and management of traditional markets, in 2007 Presidential Regulation No. 112 of 2007 was issued concerning the Arrangement and Development of Traditional Markets, Shopping Centers and Modern Shops. Then followed by the Regulation of the Minister of Trade of the Republic of Indonesia No. 53/M-Dag/Per/12/2008 concerning Guidelines for the Arrangement and Development of Traditional Markets, Shopping Centers and Modern Shops, and the Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia No. 20 of 2012 concerning the Management and Empowerment of Traditional Markets The above laws and regulations give authority to regions to organize and manage traditional markets and modern markets so that these two markets do not eliminate and kill each other, But the two markets support each other and become strategic partners in supporting development and sustaining economic growth both regionally and nationally. Departing from the above presidential regulation, several districts and cities in Indonesia began to make derivative regulations in the form of district/city regional regulations (Seran, 2014)

People's Market Innovation

Innovation is one of the key elements needed in the process of creating social entrepreneurship or efforts made to create economic value activities with the aim of overcoming social problems. The development of communication and information technology also helps facilitate the acceleration of the social innovation process of *the Platform* The internet and digital technology devices enable collaborative innovation where an innovator, user, and community collaborate using digital technology to create knowledge and solutions to various social needs (Farransahat et al., 2020)

As the development of information technology in the world changes, the industry and marketing are different, the development of internet technology and the presence of users in the virtual environment have paved the way for the emergence of electronic commerce. Nowadays most of the shopping is done through the internet E-commerce has found applications and advancements in all segments of economic life with its widespread accessibility and convenience. The main reason for this development is that e-commerce is available on the internet and instantly.

E-commerce is widely used in economic life thanks to its features. The number of e-commerce uses has become more diverse due to the number of people using desktop computers and especially mobile phones. Globalization and technological advancements have led to an unprecedented increase in innovation, competitiveness, and economic growth around the world, In this increasingly globalized world, almost every day new trends emerge Businesses must keep up with all the innovations in technology and improve themselves in order to survive in the real and digital world (Guyen, 2020)

There are two steps that are usually taken to develop traditional markets: renovation and revitalization. Renovation is an activity related to the physical improvement of buildings while revitalization is the reconceptualization of the building system (Giantari et al., 2017) the people's market revitalization program is the implementation of Law number 7 of 2014 concerning trade, article 13 paragraphs 1, 2, and 3. The market revitalization program is a solution where traditional markets are ready to improve themselves in terms of market management. Traditional revitalization programs have a positive impact on improving market management. The more organized the place where traders sell with the addition of more professional market management, traditional markets will again be looked at by consumers if the bad image that has been attached to them so far is abolished (Nayoan et al., 2021)

The connectivity of people's market protection policies in the Society 5.0 era must focus on the use of technology to increase efficiency, transparency, and market inclusion. strategies that can be applied to increase regional economic growth in disadvantaged districts of Banten Province:

- 1) Digitalization of the People's Market, through;
(1) E-Commerce Platform, developing a special e-commerce platform for the people's market that facilitates online transactions, product promotion, and inventory management. This allows market traders to reach a wider market and increase the visibility of their products.
(2) Market Management App, creating an app that allows traders to manage their sales, stocks, and financial reports. The app can also provide real-time pricing information and market trends.
- 2) Strengthening Digital Infrastructure, through;
(1) Improving Internet Connectivity, building and improving internet infrastructure in the people's market and surrounding areas, including the provision of free or affordable Wi-Fi. Ensure a stable internet network to support digital transactions and communication.
(2) Technology Facilities in the Market, Install digital payment terminals, information kiosks, and queue management systems in the people's market to facilitate transactions and interactions with technology.
- 3) Education and Training, through;
(1) Technology Training for Traders, conducting training on the use of digital technology for market traders, including how to use e-commerce platforms, digital payment systems, and market management tools.
(2) Digital Literacy Program for the Community, organizing digital literacy programs for the general public to increase understanding of technology and how to utilize it in daily life and business.
- 4) Strategic Partnerships, through;
(1) Collaboration with Technology and Startups, establishing partnerships with technology companies and startups to provide innovative digital solutions and technical support. This includes payment system integration, data analytics, and supply chain management.
(2) cooperation with educational and training institutions, in collaboration with educational institutions to organize training programs and courses related to market digitalization and entrepreneurship.
- 5) Regulatory and Policy Support, through;
(1) Data Protection Policy, implementing regulations that ensure the protection of personal data of traders and consumers, as well as the security of digital transactions.
(2) Incentives for Technology Adoption, providing

incentives such as subsidies or tax breaks for merchants who adopt digital technology and efficient management systems.

- 6) Market Promotion and Education, through; (1) Awareness and Promotion Campaign, conducting a campaign to raise awareness about the people's market and the benefits of shopping in traditional markets. Use social media and digital platforms to reach a wider audience. (2) Market Events and Festivals, organizing market events and festivals to attract visitors and introduce local products to the wider community.
- 7) Product Quality Improvement and Diversification, through; (1) Product and Service Development, encouraging merchants to improve the quality of their products and services by utilizing technology, such as the use of data to understand customer preferences and improve product offerings. (2) Diversification of Product Offerings, helping merchants to expand their product range by providing information and training on market trends and new business opportunities.
- 8) Monitoring and Evaluation, through; (1) Technology-Based Monitoring System, implement a technology-based monitoring system to track market performance, detect problems, and identify improvement opportunities. (2) Periodic Evaluation, conducting periodic evaluations of the effectiveness of policies and strategies implemented, and adjusting policies based on the results of evaluations and feedback from traders and consumers.

With these strategies, disadvantaged districts in Banten Province can take advantage of the Society 5.0 era to strengthen the protection of the people's market, increase economic growth, and reduce the gap between regions and economic centers.

CONCLUSION

Policy connectivity in the protection of the people's market is essential for a variety of reasons related to economic growth, community welfare, and social stability. Here are some points that illustrate the urgency of the people's market protection policy:

- 1) Strengthening the Local Economy is providing support for MSMEs, People's markets are often the main place for Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) to operate. Policies that protect the people's market help ensure the sustainability of MSMEs, which are crucial for the local economy. In addition, namely the creation of jobs, the people's market plays a role in the creation of local jobs. Market protection helps ensure that traders and workers in the market are not threatened by unfair practices or adverse competition.
- 2) Community Welfare is Affordable Access to Goods and Services where the people's market often provides goods and services at more affordable prices compared to large retailers. Market protection helps ensure that consumers, especially in underprivileged communities, still have access to daily necessities at reasonable prices.
- 3) Health and Safety: Protection policies can include regulations regarding food safety and health standards in the market, thus ensuring that the products sold are safe for public consumption.

- 4) Quality Improvement and Competitiveness include (1) Innovation and Quality Improvement, with adequate protection, traders in the people's market can be encouraged to improve the quality of their products and services. It can also stimulate product innovation and diversification, which in turn increases market competitiveness. (2) Access to Technology, market protection may include support for the adoption of technology, which assists merchants in terms of marketing, management, and digital transactions.
- 5) Social and Economic Stability, people's market protection policies help prevent unfair trade practices, such as monopoly or exploitation by large market players that can harm small traders and society. As an Economic Recovery, crisis or disaster situation, the people's market is often the starting point for local economic recovery. Good protection helps speed up the recovery process by ensuring that the market remains operational and functional.
- 6) Cultural Preservation and Local Identity, People's markets are often an integral part of a community's cultural and social identity. Protection policies can help preserve local traditions and market culture that are important heritage for the community.
- 7) Increasing Economic Inclusion, the protection of the people's market can increase economic inclusion by providing more equal opportunities for small and medium-sized traders to compete with large players, as well as increasing the overall economic participation of the community.
- 8) Prevention of Negative Environmental Impacts: Protection policies can include environmental aspects, such as waste management and the use of environmentally friendly packaging materials, to reduce the negative impact of the people's market on the environment.
- 9) Infrastructure and Facilities Development, protection policies can encourage the development of better market infrastructure, such as sanitation, security, and accessibility facilities, to improve the shopping and selling experience in the people's market.

Suggestion

- 1) Digital Education and Training for Traders, hold periodic training for people's market traders on the use of digital technology, including e-commerce, digital marketing, and technology-based financial management. Host workshops and seminars on how to leverage technology to improve product quality, marketing, and customer service.
- 2) Development of Digital and Physical Infrastructure; (1) Internet Connectivity: Strengthen the internet network in the people's market and surrounding areas to ensure good accessibility for traders and buyers. This includes the provision of free or affordable Wi-Fi in key markets. (2) Technology Facilities in the Market, Provide facilities such as digital payment terminals and information kiosks that allow merchants and buyers to interact with technology easily.

- 3) Partnerships with the Private Sector and Startups, Establish partnerships with technology companies and startups that can provide digital solutions, such as marketplace applications or supply chain management systems.
- 4) Supportive Policies and Regulations, Establish regulations that protect the personal data of merchants and consumers, and ensure the security of online transactions. Provide incentives and support to people's market traders who adopt digital technology, such as tax breaks or technology cost subsidies.
- 5) Promotion and Education to Consumers, including (1) Educational Campaigns, Conduct educational campaigns to increase consumer awareness about the benefits of shopping at the people's market and using technology in transactions. (2) Improving the image of the People's Market, promoting the people's market as a modern and technology-integrated place to attract more visitors and buyers.

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Landasan Hukum:

- 1) Peraturan Daerah Kabupaten Pandeglang Nomor 7 Tahun 2020 tentang penyelenggaraan pasar Pasar
- 2) Peraturan Daerah Kabupaten Lebak Nomor 10 Tahun 2018 Tentang Penataan dan Pemberdayaan Pedagangan Kaki Lima